

D7.4

Data Management Plan - update

WR

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Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
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ABBREVIATIONS

DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EU	European Union
FAIR	Fair, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
NoI	Network of Interest
WHITE	White Research SPRL
WP	Work Package
WR	Wageningen Research

DEFINITIONS

Metadata	Set of data that provides information about other data (e.g., datasets stored in a repository) specifying the characteristics of that data.
Open science	An approach to the scientific process based on open cooperative work, tools and diffusing knowledge.
Research data	H2020 definition of research data is information (particularly facts or numbers) collected to be examined and considered, and to serve as a basis for reasoning, discussion or calculation.
Research data management	The process within the research lifecycle that includes the organization, storage, preservation, security, quality assurance, allocation of persistent identifiers (PIDs) and rules and procedures for sharing of data including licensing.
Other research outputs	Results to which access can be given in the form of scientific publications, or other engineered results and processes such as software, algorithms, protocols, models, workflows and electronic notebooks.

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides the final updated version of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Data Management Plan - DMP. The initial DMP (D7.3) was prepared in the beginning of the project outlining how the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium will manage the research data collected or generated during the project. It was prepared following the Horizon Europe Data Management Template provided by the European Commission. The aim of this document was to ensure that the research data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). The DMP also provided a plan for the management of other research outputs. Further to the FAIR principles, the DMP also addresses aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects. This deliverable (D7.4) incorporates any additions made during the execution of the project from the initial version. Also reports on the datasets produced from the project.

1. Introduction

The first version of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Data Management Plan (DMP) was introduced at the beginning of the project in November 2022 (D7.3). The DMP is intended to be a living document to be updated over the course of the project. This deliverable (D7.4) provides the final version incorporating any additions made during the execution of the project. The DMP, since the early phases of the project, supported partners in considering all the relevant aspects of data management, by establishing consistent practices among partners to increase the efficiency and robustness of data handling along the project.

As part of the European Commission's goal to advance Open Science policy and practices, it is a mandatory component in Horizon Europe that all projects establish and regularly update a DMP. This document follows the Data Management Template recommended to be used by Horizon Europe beneficiaries (v1.0, 5 May 2021). It addresses the requirements for research data management of Horizon Europe as described in article 17 and specific rules set out in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement.

The DMP outlines the way that data are collected or generated within the project, how they will be organized, stored, and shared according to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.¹ It is structured following the Horizon Europe DMP template as follows:

Chapter 2: Data summary provides general information about the data usage in the project, namely the purpose and sources of data collection/generation in relation to the achievement of project objectives and data utility. Technical information about data types and formatting will also be provided.

Chapter 3: FAIR data describes the general methodologies that the project will follow to ensure that data will be managed according to the FAIR principles with sections covering each of the four principles: Fair, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

Chapter 4: Other research outputs provides plan for the management of research outputs other than data.

Chapter 5: Allocation of resources covers how project resources are allocated to the management of research data.

Chapter 6: Data security explains provisions to be in place for data security.

Chapter 7: Ethics considers any ethics or legal issues concerning data sharing and dealing with personal data.

Annex: Annex A includes the template for the form that can be used to document the datasets created in SUSTCERT4BIOBASED. The information on the datasets produced in the project is provided by filling in this template in Annex A.

Annex B provides copy of relevant sections from the Consortium agreement on dissemination and confidential information.

Annex C includes the documents used in managing collection of personal data in the project.

¹ Wilkinson, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci. Data 3:160018 doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18 (2016).

2. Data Summary

2.1 Purpose of data collection and relation to the project objectives

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project is set on fostering the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. As a coordination and support action project, the concept of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is to generate the necessary support instruments (knowledge, data, insights, and tools) and use those in deriving and communicating recommendations for key target groups: Policy makers, Sustainability system community, Industry, and Regional bioeconomy stakeholders.

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED activities are structured in 7 interlinked work packages (WPs) running for a duration of 36 months. Specific objectives were defined linking to the WPs.

1. To perform a review and analysis of existing international and EU sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for biological resources and for biobased materials and products
2. To gather data on global trade flows for biological resources and for biobased materials and products, distinguishing between certified and uncertified
3. To define and optimize a monitoring framework and indicators for systematic evaluation of the effectiveness and robustness of sustainability schemes and labels
4. To test the effectiveness and robustness of selected certification schemes and labels with the developed monitoring system
5. To assess costs and benefits (economic and internalized environmental and social ones) and evaluate feasibility of schemes/labels in selected industrial biobased value chains
6. To derive best practices and recommendations for the adoption of effective and robust sustainability schemes and labels
7. To establish and maintain continuous engagement with stakeholders especially international organizations, industrial parties, scheme owners, certifications bodies and policy makers

In order to reach their objectives, all the research WPs will collect and generate data and this data in turn can be used by other WPs.

The project had only one deliverable of type Data which is *D2.2 Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products*. Otherwise, for carrying out the research needed to achieve the specific objectives, data was collected/generated in various tasks and activities of this project. These were used as input in preparation of the other deliverables that are in a report format.

2.2 Types, formats and size of the data

Data types include derived or compiled data that concern data gathered from primary and/or secondary sources as well as data obtained from existing databases. No experimental or simulation type of data is generated in this project.

Most common type of data that is collected or produced in this project is text and numerical data. Additionally, graphical and audio-visual data are generated from this collected and produced data.

In most cases, the collected data are organized in a spreadsheet, which besides some numerical data typically contain short or long text entries. These spreadsheets have the .xlsx format. Other data formats are text documents (.pdf and .docx).

The data formats used in the project:

- Spreadsheet – MS Excel .xlsx
- Text files - MS Word .docx, and Adobe .pdf
- Multimedia – MS Power Point .ppt, Image formats: .jpg, .gif, .tiff, .png, Video formats: .mpeg, .mp4, .avi

The project did not generate large volumes of data. The size of the largest dataset is less than 7 megabytes.

2.3 The origin of the data and re-use of existing data

Literature research and stakeholder consultation was the main origin of data collection in this project.

Literature search includes scientific articles, reports from grey literature including deliverables of related research projects, documentation of existing standards, schemes and labels, and policy documents. It also includes collection of data from existing databases (e.g., market databases from Eurostat). These sources were publicly available. Irrespective of the data origin, clear source referencing was maintained.

Stakeholder consultation forms the other major source of data. This involves data collected through interviews, workshops and other forms of engagement with the stakeholders (e.g., industry actors, policy actors, sustainability system actors, regional bioeconomy actors, etc.). This also includes data that was received confidentially from industry or scheme owners for carrying out cost benefit analysis.

Furthermore, data was generated by partners within the project by analysis and assessment activities.

2.4 Data utility

Published research data from this project can be of interest to a range of stakeholders:

- Public authorities and policy makers – serve as input in policy development
- Sustainability system community – enhance the performance of standards/schemes/labels
- Scientific community – contribute to existing knowledge on the related research fields
- Research projects – following Horizon Europe or other research projects can continue to build on the data generated by SUSTCERT4BIOBASED
- Industry – increase awareness on available certification schemes/labels and their benefits

2.5 Data collected/generated in the project

Further information is provided below on the data that were collected/generated through project activities. In Annex A, information is provided on the datasets generated in the project that were either separately uploaded or part of the deliverable.

Classification of biological resources and biobased products (WP1, linked to D1.1)

As part of WP1, D1.1 classification of biological resources and biobased products was carried out which served as a reference for this project but can also be used beyond this project to facilitate a common classification system for these biological sources and products (see Table 2).

Data for analysis of synergies and trade-offs (WP1, linked to D1.3)

As part of WP1, D1.3 analysis of synergies and trade-offs were carried out. For this purpose, first the collated sustainability principles and criteria for industrial biobased systems from Task 1.2 was analysed against SDG targets. This resulted in the identification of the most relevant SDG targets for these biobased systems (see Table 3). Then for a selection of biobased value chains from different sectors a qualitative analysis was done to identify correlation between these most relevant SDG targets (see Table 4).

Data for identification of most representative biobased value chains (WP1, linked to D2.1)

As part of WP2, D2.1 identification of most representative biobased value chains was carried out. In this project six industrial sectors were considered which are textile, woodworking, plastic, pulp and paper, construction and chemical, and three biobased value chains were selected per sector. These eighteen biobased value chains were ranked using a multicriteria decision making methodology analytical hierarchy process. For each of the sub-criteria, a scale from 1 to 9 has been drawn up with a description of what each value means, and through desk research a score has been given to each value chain for each sub-criteria (see Table 5).

Data on production and trade volumes for selected bio-based products and biological resources (WP2, linked to D2.2)

As part of WP2, D2.2 database was generated on trade volumes for selected biobased value chains. This dataset contains data on trade volumes at ten (un)certified biobased product value chains analysed (that were identified in D2.1 of this project) for EU as a whole. As much as possible, biobased shares of product stages within the value chains, biological feedstock use of the products within the value chains, and certification rate of the traded products within the value chains were estimated. This dataset is organised in the form of 10 sheets per value chain analysed; each sheet contains tables and figures with estimated certified percentage of traded products in the 10 biobased value chains analysed. This D2.2 comprised of the Excel database and accompanying guidance document was submitted at the end of the first reporting period M18 – November 2023. During the second reporting period updates were carried out in collaboration with the sister projects. The final version was uploaded in May 2025 to Zenodo and is publicly available (see Table 6).

Data from review of available monitoring approached for sustainability schemes and labels (WP3, linked to D3.1)

As part of WP3, D3.1 a compilation of criteria was made from review of relevant tools (guidelines, benchmarking tool, legislation). The criteria are related to system level characteristics concerning scheme governance and management (e.g., transparency, assurance, accreditation). The review of the criteria of all the tools combined was synthesized into a list of 137 criteria, 18 subthemes, and 2 themes. Then an analysis was performed of the coverage of compiled criteria by the ten tools reviewed (see Table 7).

Data for evaluation of existing sustainability certification schemes and labels (WP3, linked to D3.2)

As part of WP3, D3.2 results from the testing of the content level of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT) on selected nine sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems were reported. For this analysis for each of the tested CSLs their relevant standards were reviewed to analyse the coverage of the defined requirements. This was done by filling in the final version of the BMT with the responses for each of the CSLs, resulting in 9 Excel documents with assessment results. It was decided not to include these detailed assessment results for the tested CSLs in the public deliverable. Rather in D3.2 a reporting template was developed to report on the findings from the assessment carried out in the Excel document. The assessment report provides information on the content of the standard with regard to sustainability principles and criteria, identified strengths, weaknesses and opportunities for improvement. These individual assessment reports per each of the assessed nine CSLs are provided in D3.2.

Compilation of requirements for assessment of robustness, comprehensiveness and effectiveness of sustainability certification schemes and labels (WP3, linked to D3.3)

As part of WP3, D3.3 the final version of the monitoring tool developed was described. This deliverable reports on the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT) that has been developed jointly by the BIOBASEDCERT cluster (comprised of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, STAR4BBS and HARMONITOR projects) to assess the robustness, comprehensiveness and effectiveness of existing voluntary sustainability certification schemes and labels (CSLs) for industrial biobased systems. The monitoring system is built around a comprehensive set of requirements designed to gather crucial information on CSLs. These requirements are structured into three levels: System Level – Assessing the governance, transparency and operational robustness of CSLs; Content Level – Evaluating the sustainability and circularity requirements set by the standards for certified operators; and Outcome Level – Measuring the impacts generated by the implementation of CSLs. The BMT is an Excel tool and provided as D3.3 together with a report describing the BMT and providing guidance on how to use it (see Table 8).

Data for cost-benefit analysis (within WP4)

As part of WP4, data was collected to carry out cost-benefit assessment on three biobased value chains (sugarcane, cotton, wood). This data was collected using the data collection template developed and reported in D4.3. Required data for this assessment was aimed to be collected from companies but this proved to be very challenging due to the sensitivity or unavailability of the data needed for the assessments. For the sugarcane value chain data was able to be obtained through a certification scheme. This data attained was treated as confidential and was presented anonymously. This data collection approach was also tried for the two other value chains but in the end was not possible due to confidentiality concerns. For the cotton and wood value chains assessments relied on extensive literature search and data was gathered from secondary sources. The collected data for these three biobased value chains were used in the cost-benefit analysis performed and reported in D4.4.

Data for deriving recommendations to four key targeted stakeholder groups (within WP5)

As part of WP5, D5.1 key insights from the project were reported, providing an overview of research findings and presenting targeted recommendations for key stakeholders involved in the European bioeconomy. These recommendations are categorised for the four target audiences of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project: policymakers, standard writers and scheme owners, industrial actors, and regional actors. In Annex, all the recommendations are listed with source and the applicable relevant stakeholder groups are marked (see Table 9). Additionally, within WP5 thematic briefs were prepared for each of these four target groups. This was done through engagement with

these stakeholders through dedicated interview, workshops and/or engagement events. The information collected from these exchanges were used as input in the developed briefs which are reported as deliverables D5.2-5.6.

Data regarding dissemination and communication activities (within WP6)

Data collected from events:

- Data was collected during the organization of events and workshops in the framework of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project (such as list of participants including names, type of stakeholder, demographic information about the attendees, images etc.)
- Data was collected from the project's participation in external events for its further promotion and the dissemination of the results.

The data collected from the events were both quantitative and qualitative (.xlsx, .doc) and enabled the project partners to keep track and report the implemented engagement activities.

Data collected from the social media accounts:

The social media (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube) statistics were monitored in a regular basis in order to better fine-tune our strategy and content and engage as many stakeholders as possible. Both qualitative and quantitative data was collected including information such as the number of followers, demographics of the followers, impressions, likes etc. The results obtained by the social media metrics was monitored through an excel template and the analysis of the results was saved in a doc. document.

Data collected through our website:

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website is using cookies in order to remember visitors' actions and preferences (such as login, language, font size and other display preferences). In addition, Google Analytics was used to better understand how visitors interact with the website. A privacy policy has been developed and is accessible by all visitors through the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website. The policy complies with the most recent EU regulations and the most updated version is available on the website (the website policy can be found in D6.2 SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package).

Data collected through our Newsletter:

MailChimp is used for the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Newsletters. The data collected during the registration to the Newsletter through the website (e.g e-mail addresses) is stored in the MailChimp platform and was used only for sending the bi-annual issues to the recipients.

Data collected through the Network of Interest (NoI):

Data was collected from the members of the NoI during the registration process that enables us to contact them and engage them in future activities (e.g e-mail, name, profession etc.). Some of this information (name, profession) were also displayed on the website. In addition, information such as demographics were collected in order to keep track of the members characteristics and to include them in our internal/external reporting (this information will be only available to the consortium and the EU commission and only aggregated, anonymised data were included in our reports). All NoI members follow a 3-step registration process that ensures GDPR compliance (more information on that is provided in Annex C and in the D6.2 SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package).

3. FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable) Data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Discoverability/identifiability of data

As requested in the GA, the data produced and considered open for re-use were deposited in a trusted repository (Zenodo) and is locatable with a unique and persistent identifier (e.g., DOI). All partners make use of Digital Object Identifier - DOI to make datasets produced citable for publication. The global consortium DataCite is the official DOI registration agency for research data and grey literature. The chosen data repositories need to support standard descriptive metadata to ensure datasets indexing and discoverability also by machines. It should be compatible and compliant with OpenAIRE guidelines.¹ The repository chosen in this project, Zenodo², satisfies these requirements where a DOI is issued to every published record. Metadata of Zenodo are compliant with DataCite Metadata Schema³ list of core metadata properties chosen for an accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes. Metadata of each record in Zenodo is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing and sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

A Zenodo community was created for this project and all datasets and approved deliverables were uploaded here: [SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project](#)

3.1.2 Naming convention and versioning

This DMP identifies the following common rules for dataset naming and versioning in order to improve data visibility, discoverability, citation and tracking. The version number of the dataset are added at the end of the title to help identifying the dataset updates. The recommended title for each dataset consists of:

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED_<Deliverable number > _<Short title of dataset>_<Version>

An example: SUSTCERT4BIOBASED_D1.1_Classification of biological resources and biobased products_v1.0

Each dataset should have a version log specifying the version, data, changes and responsible partner.

A template of the form to document the key characteristics of the datasets was created in D7.3 and it is included in the Annex A. In this deliverable, D7.4, this template was used in reporting the datasets generated in the project. These are included in Annex A, following the template.

3.1.3 Keywords

For each dataset, the responsible partner provides a set of selected keywords aiming to maximize discoverability. These are included in the form to document key information for each SUSTCERT4BIOBASED dataset (see Annex A).

¹ <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/index.html>

² <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>

³ <https://schema.datacite.org/>

3.2 Making data accessible

3.2.1 *Repository*

The data and metadata that is generated as part of research related to project activities will be stored in the project SharePoint site (accessible to the consortium) which serves as a central repository for the project. This facilitates secure data sharing between the WPs and partners. It also serves as an archive for all the documentation produced along the project lifetime.

The data produced and considered open for re-use will be deposited in a trusted repository. For this Zenodo is considered the repository of choice as described in section 3.1.1. A community was created in Zenodo for this project where research outputs are made publicly available. Additionally, the approved deliverables are available on the project website and partners can include the datasets they (co)authored to their institutional repositories.

3.2.2 *Open accessibility of data*

The management of the data produced during the project aims to ensure open access taking also into consideration the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle, to ensure the adoption of suitable measures to preserve project results that can contain sensitive information.

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project is fully committed to open science best practices. The default approach will be to make datasets publicly available (openly available, digitally, online, and free of charge) as soon as possible with as few exceptions as possible. However, making datasets public will not be the aim in itself. Some datasets generated in the project may be so specifically geared toward a project task or a report deliverable that there is no apparent use for it outside the project. In that case, the dataset would not be published.

Moreover, openly sharing data may not be possible considering the confidentiality obligations and the obligation to protect personal data. As for several project activities, direct consultation with stakeholders were made (e.g., interviews and workshops) and sensitive data were collected from companies and scheme owners. Sensitive data attained was treated as confidential and was anonymized and aggregated to ensure that the data owner will not be connected to this information in any reports. Regarding personal data collected in the project, data will be controlled and processed based on informed consent, in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679) and other relevant applicable EU and national regulations, protecting the data subjects' rights and freedoms concerning the processing of their personal data. This will include, for example, the provision of a framework for Data Sharing agreement with each data delivering party. Data that is collected in this way cannot be made public and in reporting they will be anonymized and aggregated to protect private and sensitive information so that it cannot be associated with an organization. During the project and for 5 years after its completion, the partners will preserve the confidentiality of any data, documents or other material identified as confidential in relation to the project execution. Publications of project outputs other than the public deliverables need to comply with the Article 13 Confidentiality of the Grant Agreement and specific provisions in the Consortium Agreement (see Annex B for a copy of relevant sections). Furthermore, data collected from the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website analytics, social media accounts and Newsletter subscriptions will be closed and will be available only to the consortium and the EU commission. Only statistics might be shared where the data will be aggregated and anonymized.

Data is published using standard file formats. Therefore, there will be no need to use specifically tailored software to access and read project datasets.

3.2.3 *Open accessibility of metadata*

Metadata will be publicly accessible and licensed under public domain (CC0) through the trusted Zenodo repository. The repository services offered by Zenodo are free of charge and enable peers to share and preserve research data and other research outputs in any size and format: datasets, images, presentations, publications and software. The digital data and the associated metadata is preserved through well-established practices such as mirroring and periodic backups. Metadata at Zenodo are stored in high-availability database servers at CERN. Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Metadata vocabularies, standards, and methods will be used to increase the interoperability of the data collected/generated using community-endorsed data standards. For example, data interoperability will be facilitated through Zenodo, since its metadata will be stored internally in JSON format according to a defined JSON schema. Further SUSTCERT4BIOBASED will assure the use of common and interoperable formats, like those supported by Excel, Word and Acrobat.

3.4 Increase data re-use

3.4.1 *Data licensing*

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED publishes its openly available data via the repository under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) to ensure that any interested third-party can re-use it. Also, consortium implements quality assurance (e.g. peer review of methods and data summaries) and quality control (technical checks on data consistency, integrity, and correctness) activities of the reported data.

3.4.2 *Re-usability of data during and at the end of the project*

To be reusable (meta)data are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. Metadata of deposited data provide information about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action. Each record at Zenodo contains a minimum of DataCite's mandatory terms, with optionally additional DataCite recommended terms and Zenodo's enrichments.

All project publications will include citations to repositories that host the data underlying the results, together with any information needed to replicate, validate, and/or reuse the results and analysis of the data.

Where open access is not possible to the data needed to validate the conclusions of a publication that reports original results (due to restrictions explained in section 3.2.2), authors will provide the relevant access needed to validate the conclusions to the extent their legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded.

In cases where data has been obtained from a third party and restrictions apply to the availability of the data, all necessary information required for a reader to access the data by the same means as the authors will be included.

4. Other research outputs

All deliverables of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED are public deliverables meaning these reports are made available for public in EU portal immediately after approval. Other form of research output will be scientific publications.

All scientific articles will be submitted to peer-reviewed journals which is essential in ensuring quality. The partners will provide open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. Partners have the possibility to publish at no costs in Open Research Europe, the European Commission open access publishing. Additionally, publishing venues such as Wiley and Elsevier will be considered. Scientific publications will be immediately open accessible through a trusted repository ("green" or "gold" open access). Publishers often charge fees, so-called Article Processing Charges (APCs) for publishing articles Gold Open Access. WR has national Open Access agreements with several major academic publishers to publish without costs.¹ Green Open Access (self-archiving) provides an alternative option, free of charge, to make closed access article openly available in an online repository such as institutional repository such as Research@WUR. Articles will be published under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY).

Additionally, any tools that will be generated by the project will be publicly available (openly available, digitally, online, and free of charge) as soon as possible accompanied by necessary guidance to use them.

As part of the project two peer-reviewed scientific articles were published in Sustainability journal and are open access (see further information in D6.3 and D6.8). Additionally, the BIOBASEDCERT tool developed will be publicly available (openly available, digitally, online, and free of charge) on the project website as well as project's Zenodo community accompanied by guidance document (see Table 8).

5. Allocation of resources

The project will take advantage of available free software and services (e.g., Zenodo) that will be used to make the data of the project open and FAIR. This requires no financial resources to be allocated for storage, cloud, hosting, IT infrastructures etc. and providing open access to research data. The costs will be related to personnel costs for managing the data.

Tasks involving data management are present in all stages of the project. The leaders of the task(s) generating each dataset has the responsibility of the correct implementation of the provisions in the DMP. Costs related to data management and documentation related to these tasks will be covered in the respective WPs. Additionally, it will be necessary to conduct quality control of the data reported which will be the responsibility of the WP leaders. As project coordinator, WR will be responsible for preparing the updates of the DMP, general coordination and providing guidance on data management. Costs associated with these activities is included in WP7.

There can be costs involved in providing open access to scientific publications. As per Grant Agreement publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are

¹ <https://www.wur.nl/en/library/researchers/open-access/open-access-agreements-and-discounts.htm>

eligible costs. WUR has national open access agreements with major publishers which the project can benefit from where the WUR corresponding authors can publish in open access for free.

Resources for long term preservation, associated costs and potential value, as well as how data will be kept beyond the project and how long, will be discussed by the whole consortium during General Assembly meetings.

6. Data security

The data and metadata that is generated as part of research related to project activities will be stored in the project SharePoint site which serves as a central repository for the project. This repository is only accessible to the consortium and provide secure storage and transfer of (sensitive) data of the project. Access requires two-factor authentication to validate the members of the site who are allowed access. Microsoft offers extensive protection in multiple layers: physical data center security, network security, access security, application security, and data security. Data is protected in-transit and at-rest using encryption (at the disk level using BitLocker encryption and at the file level using keys). Data is mirrored in at least two datacenters.¹

The data produced and considered open for re-use will be deposited in a trusted repository such as Zenodo which will ensure data security. Zenodo is hosted by CERN which makes sure that their servers always have the latest security controls to protect the data. Data is stored in CERN's EOS service in an 18 petabytes disk cluster. Each file copy has two replicas located on different disk servers. Metadata are stored with 12-hourly backup cycle with one backup sent to tape storage once a week.² This repository will provide long term preservation and curation of data.

Finally, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website has been developed in WordPress and is managed only by WHITE which holds the password to the dashboard. Similarly, the MailChimp account is also password protected and is only accessible by WHITE. All Newsletter subscribers receive a confirmation e-mail after their subscription that ensures their willingness to receive the newsletters. WordPress and MailChimp are platforms that respect the GDPR regulation.

7. Ethics

The action must be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles.

The partners must process personal data under the Agreement in compliance with the applicable EU, international and national law on data protection (in particular, Regulation 2016/67916, General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR³) in accordance with Article 15 of the GA.

The consortium will ensure that personal data is:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects

¹ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/sharepoint/safeguarding-your-data>

² <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC ('GDPR')

- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data is processed and
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the data.

Data collection mainly related to stakeholder engagement activities and workshops will be compliant with GDPR. Before collecting any data, the person involved will be asked to sign an informed consent form explaining the project and the use of the data, collection, storage and cancellation.

The following documents related to personal data are provided in Annex C in this deliverable:

- *Privacy policy* including information on how and what type of personal data is collected, what will be done with personal data and how personal data will be secured
- *Information sheet* on the project, the duration, contact details and information on their rights
- *Informed consent form* for agreeing to participate in activities of the project, acknowledgement that they know their rights and that the research data will be anonymized

“A good example of this procedure is already implemented in our Network of Interest registration process on our website”

In reporting in public domain the data will be anonymized and aggregated to protect private and sensitive information so that it cannot be associated with an individual or organization.

Data collected and produced as part of the project will be done in accordance with the ethical principles, notably to avoid fabrication, falsification, plagiarism or other research misconduct.

8. Conclusion

How the data will be organized, stored, shared, accessed and preserved during the project lifetime and beyond is an essential consideration. Data Management Plan, although part of the of WP7 Management and coordination, has connections with all the previous WPs that collect and/or generate data. WR is responsible for creating and maintaining the DMP throughout the project. The initial version of the DMP was developed at M6 (November 2022) and supported project partners in considering all the relevant aspects and provided guidance regarding data management. Each project partner was responsible for managing their data according to this DMP. This deliverable D7.4 provides the updated final version of the DMP at the end of the project (M36, May 2025). In the first version of DMP a template of the form to describe the datasets of the project was provided. This final version of DMP reflects on the changes over the course of the project execution and includes the documentation of datasets produced by the project.

Annex A: Form to document key information for each SUSTCERT4BIOBASED dataset

Table 1. Dataset reporting template

Topic	Description
Dataset identifier	[dataset title, see section 3.1.2 for guidance]
Dataset description	[short description on the data: This dataset contains data on, This dataset is organised as ...]
Dataset version	[e.g., v1.0 (final)]
Associated WP	[e.g., WP1]
Associated Task	[e.g., T1.1]
Key contact/creator	[name and organisation, if available also include ORCID]
Other contributors	[other contributing partners' name and organisation]
Data format and size	[e.g., Excel spreadsheet, 1 MB]
Keywords	[at least 5 keywords associated with the dataset]
Key data sources	[e.g., scientific literature review, ... database, workshop, audit]
Key users of data	[see section 2.4]
Related deliverable/publication	[specify if dataset related to input for preparation of a certain deliverable or a publication]
Dataset public/openly accessible?	[yes/no]
If No, justification	[e.g., used for internal analysis in the preparation of deliverable Dx.y / contains sensitive or confidential data - GDPR requirement to protect personal data]
If Public, Repository(-ies) with link	[e.g., project website, Zenodo]
If Public, Licence	[Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY)]
If Public, DOI	[DOI]

Table 2. Dataset from D1.1, classification of biological resources and biobased products

Topic	Description
Dataset identifier	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED_D1.1_Classification of biological resources and biobased products_v1.0
Dataset description	Annex A of deliverable D1.1 provides the classification of biological resources. Annex B of deliverable D1.1 provides the classification of biobased products
Dataset version	v1.0
Associated WP	WP1
Associated Task	T1.1
Key contact/creator	Víctor Fernández Ocamica; ORCID: https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0976-0121
Other contributors	Monique Bernardes Figueiredo, Barbara Palacino Blazquez
Data format and size	pdf, 1.4 MB
Keywords	Classification, biological resources, biobased products
Key data sources	The Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community (NACE, PRODCOM), Scientific literature
Key users of data	Industry, public authorities, sustainability system community, scientific people
Related deliverable/publication	D1.1
Dataset public/openly accessible?	Yes
If No, justification	-
If Public, Repository(-ies) with link	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/records/14283702
If Public, Licence	CC BY 4.0
If Public, DOI	10.5281/zenodo.14283702

Table 3. Dataset from D1.3, alignment matrix of the SDG targets with the principles and criteria for sustainability of bio-based systems

Topic	Description
Dataset identifier	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED_D1.3_Alignment matrix of the SDG targets with the principles and criteria for sustainability of bio-based systems_v1.0
Dataset description	This file contains the matrix resulting from the matching exercise between the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the sustainability principles and criteria for biobased products. The matrix identifies the specific SDG targets that are most relevant for evaluating the sustainability of industrial biobased systems.
Dataset version	v1.0
Associated WP	WP1
Associated Task	T1.4
Key contact/creator	Víctor Fernández Ocamica; ORCID: https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0976-0121
Other contributors	Monique Bernardes Figueiredo, Barbara Palacino Blazquez
Data format and size	xlsx; 220 KB
Keywords	SDGs, sustainability criteria, biobased economy, matching matrix
Key data sources	T1.2 collated sustainability principles and criteria, and SDG targets (Final list of proposed Sustainable Development Goal indicators available online)
Key users of data	Industry, public authorities, sustainability system community, scientific people
Related deliverable/publication	D1.3
Dataset public/openly accessible?	Yes
If No, justification	-
If Public, Repository(-ies) with link	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/records/15349421
If Public, Licence	CC BY 4.0
If Public, DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15349375

Table 4. Dataset from D1.3, qualitative analyses of selected value chains against the applicable SDG targets

Topic	Description
Dataset identifier	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED_D1.3_Qualitative analyses of selected value chains against the applicable SDG targets_v1.0
Dataset description	This file presents the correlation analysis between the selected value chains against the identified SDG targets that are most relevant for evaluating the sustainability of industrial biobased systems
Dataset version	v1.0
Associated WP	WP1
Associated Task	T1.4
Key contact/creator	Víctor Fernández Ocamica; ORCID: https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0976-0121
Other contributors	Monique Bernardes Figueiredo, Barbara Palacino Blazquez
Data format and size	xlsx; 266 KB
Keywords	SDG targets, sustainability assessment, bioeconomy, sustainability, biobased value chains
Key data sources	Scientific literature, SDG targets (Final list of proposed Sustainable Development Goal indicators available online)
Key users of data	Industry, public authorities, sustainability system community, scientific people
Related deliverable/publication	D1.3
Dataset public/openly accessible?	yes
If No, justification	-
If Public, Repository(-ies) with link	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/records/15349375
If Public, Licence	CC BY 4.0
If Public, DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15349375

Table 5. Dataset from D2.1, Identification of the most representative biobased value chains

Topic	Description
Dataset identifier	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED_D2.1 Identification of the most representative biobased value chains_v1.0
Dataset description	A multicriteria decision making methodology based on the Analytic Hierarchy Process was used to rank the selected 18 biobased value chains
Dataset version	v1.0
Associated WP	WP2
Associated Task	T2.1
Key contact/creator	Víctor Fernández Ocamica; ORCID: https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0976-0121
Other contributors	Sebastian Zapata Habas, Cristina Lázaro, Monique Bernardes Figueiredo
Data format and size	pdf; 1.6 MB
Keywords	Biobased value chains, sustainability, analytic hierarchy process
Key data sources	Scientific and grey literature, Expert inputs for valuation of the criteria and sub-criteria
Key users of data	Industry, public authorities, sustainability system community, scientific people
Related deliverable/publication	D2.1
Dataset public/openly accessible?	yes
If No, justification	-
If Public, Repository(-ies) with link	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/records/15174219
If Public, Licence	CC BY 4.0
If Public, DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15174219

Table 6. Dataset from D2.2, Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products

Topic	Description
Dataset identifier	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED_D2.2_Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products_v1.0
Dataset description	This dataset contains data on trade volumes at different stages of 10 (un)certified biobased product value chains analysed (which are identified in Deliverable 2.1 of this project) for EU as a whole. As much as possible, it contains estimates on biobased shares of product stages within the value chains, biological feedstock use of the products within the value chains, and certification rate of the traded products within the value chains. This dataset is organised in the form of 10 sheets per value chain analysed; each sheet contains tables and figures with estimated certified percentage of traded products in the 10 biobased value chains analysed.
Dataset version	v1.0
Associated WP	WP2
Associated Task	T2.2
Key contact/creator	Myrna van Leeuwen; ORCID: 0000-0003-1902-4531
Other contributors	Bobby Tsvetkov, Frans Godeschalk, David Verhoog (WR-WSER)
Data format and size	xlsx; 6.7 MB
Keywords	Trade volumes; certification, biobased value chains, biological resources
Key data sources	Eurostat, COMEXT, COMTRADE, FAOSTAT, Prodcum; ITC standard maps; Biomonitor project; expert knowledge; certification scheme websites
Key users of data	Industry, public authorities, sustainability system community, scientific people
Related deliverable/publication	D2.2
Dataset public/openly accessible?	yes
If No, justification	-
If Public, Repository(-ies) with link	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/records/15349353
If Public, Licence	CC BY 4.0
If Public, DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15349353

Table 7. Dataset from D3.1, Qualitative analyses of selected value chains against the applicable SDG targets

Topic	Description
Dataset identifier	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED_D3.1 Review of existing monitoring approaches for schemes and labels_v1.0
Dataset description	Annex A of D3.1 provides the compilation of the criteria from review of relevant tools and analysis of the coverage of compiled criteria by each tool
Dataset version	v1.0
Associated WP	WP3
Associated Task	T3.1
Key contact/creator	Mariana López Dávila
Other contributors	-
Data format and size	pdf; 739 KB
Keywords	Sustainability certification schemes, benchmarking tools, guidelines, criteria
Key data sources	ISEAL guidelines, assessment tools, benchmarking tools, and legislations
Key users of data	Industry, public authorities, sustainability system community, scientific people
Related deliverable/publication	D3.1
Dataset public/openly accessible?	yes
If No, justification	-
If Public, Repository(-ies) with link	Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/records/15174447
If Public, Licence	CC BY 4.0
If Public, DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15174447

Table 8. Dataset from D3.3, BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool - BMT

Topic	Description
Dataset identifier	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED_D3.3 BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool_v1.0
Dataset description	This deliverable reports on the final version of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT) that has been developed jointly by the BIOBASEDCERT cluster (comprised of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, STAR4BBS and HARMONITOR projects) to assess the robustness, comprehensiveness and effectiveness of existing voluntary sustainability certification schemes and labels (CSLs) for industrial biobased systems. BMT is structured in three levels: system level, content level and outcome level. The tool is Excel document. It is accompanied by a report explaining the tool and guidance notes on how to use it.
Dataset version	v1.0
Associated WP	WP3
Associated Task	T3.5
Key contact/creator	Iris Vural Gursel (Wageningen Research); Laura Väyrynen (ECOS)
Other contributors	-
Data format and size	Tool xlsx; 322 KB and Report pdf; 2.4 MB
Keywords	Sustainability certification schemes and labels, biobased products, effectiveness, robustness, monitoring
Key data sources	Scientific and grey literature, legislation, sustainability standards, guidelines, monitoring tools
Key users of data	Industry, public authorities, sustainability system community, scientific people
Related deliverable/publication	D3.3
Dataset public/openly accessible?	yes
If No, justification	-
If Public, Repository(-ies) with link	Zenodo, will be available here
If Public, Licence	CC BY 4.0
If Public, DOI	will be available through Zenodo

Table 9. Dataset from D5.1, Summary of project deliverables findings

Topic	Description
Dataset identifier	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED_D5.1 Summary of project deliverables findings_v1.0
Dataset description	This document collates the key insights from the project, providing an overview of research findings and presenting targeted recommendations for key stakeholders involved in the European bioeconomy. These recommendations are categorised by the stakeholder groups that were identified as the four target audiences of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project: policymakers, standard writers and scheme owners, industrial actors, and regional actors. In Annex all the recommendations are listed with source and the applicable relevant stakeholder groups are marked.
Dataset version	v1.0
Associated WP	WP5
Associated Task	T5.1
Key contact/creator	Laura Väyrynen
Other contributors	-
Data format and size	Report pdf; 1.6 MB
Keywords	Sustainability certification schemes, biobased products, cost benefit analysis, monitoring system/tool
Key data sources	Project deliverables from WPs 1-4
Key users of data	Industry, public authorities, sustainability system community, scientific people
Related deliverable/publication	D5.1
Dataset public/openly accessible?	yes
If No, justification	-
If Public, Repository(-ies) with link	Zenodo, will be available here
If Public, Licence	CC BY 4.0
If Public, DOI	will be available through Zenodo

Annex B: Sections from the Consortium Agreement on Dissemination and Confidential Information

8.4.2 Dissemination of own (including jointly owned) Results

8.4.2.1

During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, the dissemination of own Results by one or several Parties including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 17.4 of the Grant Agreement and its Annex 5, Section Dissemination, subject to the following provisions.

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 30 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 25 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

8.4.2.2

An objection is justified if

- a) the protection of the objecting Party's Results or Background would be adversely affected, or
- b) the objecting Party's legitimate interests in relation to its Results or Background would be significantly harmed, or
- c) the proposed publication includes Confidential Information of the objecting Party.

The objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications.

8.4.2.3

If an objection has been raised the involved Parties shall discuss how to overcome the justified grounds for the objection on a timely basis (for example by amendment to the planned publication and/or by protecting information before publication) and the objecting Party shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if appropriate measures are taken following the discussion.

8.4.2.4

The objecting Party can request a publication delay of not more than 90 calendar days from the time it raises such an objection. After 90 calendar days the publication is permitted, provided that the objections of the objecting Party have been addressed.

8.4.3 Dissemination of another Party's unpublished Results or Background

A Party shall not include in any dissemination activity another Party's Results or Background without obtaining the owning Party's prior written approval, unless they are already published.

10. Non-disclosure of information

10.1

All information in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Party (the "Disclosing Party") to any other Party (the "Recipient") in connection with the Project during its implementation and which has been explicitly marked as "confidential" at the time of disclosure, or

when disclosed orally has been identified as confidential at the time of disclosure and has been confirmed and designated in writing within 15 calendar days from oral disclosure at the latest as confidential information by the Disclosing Party, is “Confidential Information”.

10.2

The Recipients hereby undertake in addition and without prejudice to any commitment on non-disclosure under the Grant Agreement, for a period of 5 years after the end of the Project:

- not to use Confidential Information otherwise than for the purpose for which it was disclosed;
- not to disclose Confidential Information without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party;
- to ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis; and
- to return to the Disclosing Party, or destroy, on request all Confidential Information that has been disclosed to the Recipients including all copies thereof and to delete all information stored in a machine-readable form to the extent practically possible. The Recipients may keep a copy to the extent it is required to keep, archive or store such Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable laws and regulations or for the proof of on-going obligations provided that the Recipient complies with the confidentiality obligations herein contained with respect to such copy.

10.3

The Recipients shall be responsible for the fulfilment of the above obligations on the part of their employees or third parties involved in the Project and shall ensure that they remain so obliged, as far as legally possible, during and after the end of the Project and/or after the termination of the contractual relationship with the employee or third party.

10.4

The above shall not apply for disclosure or use of Confidential Information, if and in so far as the Recipient can show that:

- the Confidential Information has become or becomes publicly available by means other than a breach of the Recipient’s confidentiality obligations;
- the Disclosing Party subsequently informs the Recipient that the Confidential Information is no longer confidential;
- the Confidential Information is communicated to the Recipient without any obligation of confidentiality by a third party who is to the best knowledge of the Recipient in lawful possession thereof and under no obligation of confidentiality to the Disclosing Party;
- the disclosure or communication of the Confidential Information is foreseen by provisions of the Grant Agreement;
- the Confidential Information, at any time, was developed by the Recipient completely independently of any such disclosure by the Disclosing Party;
- the Confidential Information was already known to the Recipient prior to disclosure, or
- the Recipient is required to disclose the Confidential Information in order to comply with applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order, subject to the provision Section 10.7 hereunder.

10.5

The Recipient shall apply the same degree of care with regard to the Confidential Information disclosed within the scope of the Project as with its own confidential and/or proprietary information, but in no case less than reasonable care.

10.6

Each Recipient shall promptly inform the relevant Disclosing Party by written notice of any unauthorised disclosure, misappropriation or misuse of Confidential Information after it becomes aware of such unauthorised disclosure, misappropriation or misuse.

10.7

If any Recipient becomes aware that it will be required, or is likely to be required, to disclose Confidential Information in order to comply with applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order, it shall, to the extent it is lawfully able to do so, prior to any such disclosure

- notify the Disclosing Party, and
- comply with the Disclosing Party's reasonable instructions to protect the confidentiality of the information.

Annex C: Documents related to personal data

The following documents related to personal data are provided in Annex C in this deliverable:

- *Privacy policy* including information on how and what type of personal data is collected, what will be done with personal data and how personal data will be secured
- *Information sheet* on the project, the duration, contact details and information on their rights
- *Informed consent form* for agreeing to participate in activities of the project, acknowledgement that they know their rights and that the research data will be anonymized

Annex C1. Privacy Policy

The Privacy Policy governs personal data collection and use in SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project. It can be personalized to specific project activity where personal data is to be collected.

How we collect your personal data

We collect personal data both directly and indirectly:

Directly. We obtain personal data directly from individuals in a variety of ways, including but not limited to the following cases:

- an individual subscribes to our newsletter/s;
- an individual registers to attend in meetings and/or events (e.g. conferences, webinars, etc.) we host and during attendance at such events;
- we establish cooperative relationships with an individual;
- we provide professional services pursuant to our contract with the European Commission;
- an individual participates in an interview or survey organised and performed by us.

Indirectly. We obtain personal data indirectly about individuals from a variety of sources, including:

- our research partners;
- our networks and contacts;
- public and open data sources such as public registers, news articles and internet searches;
- social and professional networking sites (e.g. LinkedIn).

What types of data we collect?

We only collect the data that are necessary for the smooth implementation of our project. These data fall into the following categories:

- contact details (name/ surname, e-mail address, street address, mobile phone number, land line phone number);
- professional information (job title, organisation, field of expertise);
- demographics (e.g. age, gender, nationality);
- information about what a person knows or believes.
- videos and photos (from people that attend our events).

Bases of lawful processing

We process personal data on the following legal bases:

Legal obligations – for processing activities required for compliance both with applicable national and European legislation, as well as with the specific legal and regulatory framework of the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union.

Consent – for processing activities such as organisation of surveys and interviews, completing of questionnaires and dissemination of project's results.

Contractual obligations – for processing activities such as reporting to the European Commission and complying with project's publicity obligations.

What we do with your personal data

We process your personal data with the purpose of:

- Conducting research (e.g., interviews, surveys);
- Disseminating our project's results to different types of stakeholders;
- Sending invitations and providing access to guests attending our events and webinars;
- Administering, maintaining, and ensuring the security of our information systems, applications, and websites;
- Processing online requests or queries, including responding to communications from individuals;
- Complying with contractual, legal, and regulatory obligations.

How we secure your personal data when we process it

We continuously apply a personal data risk assessment process to identify, analyse, and evaluate the security risks that may threaten your personal data. Based on the results of this risk assessment, we define and apply a set of both technical and organisational measures to mitigate the above security risks, including but not limited to:

- Data Protection Policies to guide our personnel when processing your data;
- Non-Disclosure Agreements with our personnel;
- Back up process, antimalware protection, access control mechanisms, etc.

Do we share personal data with third parties?

We may occasionally share personal data with trusted third parties to help us deliver efficient and quality services. When we do so, we ensure that recipients are contractually bound to safeguard the data we entrust to them before we share the data. We may engage with several or all the following categories of recipients:

- Parties that support us as we provide our services (e.g., cloud-based software services such as Dropbox, Microsoft Teams, Google Drive);
- Our professional advisers, including lawyers, auditors, and insurers;
- Dissemination services providers (e.g., MailChimp);
- Law enforcement or other government and regulatory agencies or other third parties as required by, and in accordance with applicable law or regulation;
- The European Commission, according to our relevant contractual obligations.

Do we transfer your personal data outside the European Economic Area?

We do not own file servers located outside the European Economic Area (EEA). However, some partners may use cloud and/or marketing services from reputable providers such as SharePoint, DropBox, MailChimp, Google, etc., situated both inside and outside the EEA. We always check that such providers comply with the relevant GDPR requirements before start using their services.

Do we use cookies?

Our website uses cookies. A statement will be sent to your browser explaining the use of cookies. Cookies are small text files which are saved on your computer, mobile phone or tablet. They allow the website to remember your actions and preferences (such as login, language, font size and other display preferences) so you don't have to keep re-entering them whenever you come back to the site. You can control and/ or delete cookies as you wish. If you do this, however, you may need to manually adjust your preferences every time you visit a site. For more information on how to manage cookies, please visit: <http://www.aboutcookies.org/>

We use tools like Google Analytics to better understand how visitors interact with our website. This provides us with important information to enable the site to work better. The information collected is not linked to your personal data. For more information on the cookies set by Google Analytics, please visit: <http://code.google.com/apis/analytics/docs/concepts/gaConceptsCookies.html>

The following cookies are used by Google Analytics:

Name	Typical content	Cookie expires after
_ga	Used to distinguish users	2 years
_gat	Used to throttle request rate	1 minute
_gid	Used to distinguish users	24 hours

Your rights

You have the following rights regarding our processing of your personal data:

- **Right to withdraw consent** – You can withdraw consent that you have previously given to one or more specified purposes to process your personal data. This will not affect the lawfulness of any processing carried out before you withdraw your consent.
- **Right of access** – You can ask us to verify whether we are processing personal data about you and, if so, to have access to a copy of such data.
- **Right to rectification and erasure** – You can ask us to correct our records if you believe they contain incorrect or incomplete information about you or ask us to erase your personal data after you withdraw your consent to processing or when we no longer need it for the purpose it was originally collected.
- **Right to restriction of processing** – You can ask us to temporarily restrict our processing of your personal data if you contest the accuracy of your personal data, prefer to restrict its use rather than having us erase it, or need us to preserve it for you to establish, exercise or defend a legal claim. A temporary restriction may apply while verifying whether we have overriding legitimate grounds to process it. You can ask us to inform you before we lift that temporary processing restriction.

- **Right to data portability** – In some circumstances, where you have provided personal data to us, you can ask us to transmit that personal data (in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format) directly to another entity.
- **Right to object** – You can object to our use of your personal data for direct marketing purposes, including profiling or where processing has taken the form of automated decision-making. However, we may need to keep some minimal information (e.g., e-mail address) to comply with your request to cease marketing to you.
- **Right to make a complaint to your local Data Protection Authority (DPA)** (see https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/structure/data-protection-authorities/index_en.htm) regarding any concerns you may have about our data handling practices.

To ask us to do anything of the above, you can contact us by e-mail info@sustcert4biobased.eu. We will promptly examine your request against the relevant requirements of the laws and regulations governing privacy and personal data protection, and we will answer the latest within 30 days after receiving your request. We will ask you for some kind of identification (e.g. photocopy of your identity card or passport) to avoid non-authorised revealing your personal data. If, due to the complexity of the request or a multitude of requests, we are unable to respond promptly, we will notify you within 30 days of any delay, which in no case may exceed two months from the expiration of the 30-day deadline.

How long do we retain personal data?

We retain personal data to provide our services, stay in contact with you and to comply with applicable laws, regulations, and contractual obligations to which we are subject. Please note that we are obliged to retain data concerning projects funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union for up to five years after the project's end (unless auditors request further retention). After the expiry of the retention period, and unless further legitimate grounds for retention arise, we will dispose of personal data securely.

Disclaimer of liability for third party websites

Although our site may contain links to third-party sites, including the sites of the consortium partners, we are not responsible for the privacy practices or content of these sites and we expressly disclaim any liability for any loss or damage that may be caused by the use of these links. We do not monitor the privacy practices or the content of these sites. If you have any questions about the privacy practices of another site, you should contact the site's responsible personnel. We suggest you read the privacy policy of each website you interact with, before allowing the collection and use of your personal data.

We may also provide social media features that allow you to share information on your social networks and interact with our project on various social media sites. The use of these social media features may result in the collection or sharing of information about you. We recommend that you check the privacy policies and regulations of the social networking sites you interact with, so that you can be sure that you understand what information may be collected, used and disclosed by these sites.

Children

We do not knowingly collect, use, or disclose information from children under the age of 16. If we learn that we have collected the personal information of a child under 16 we will take steps to delete the information as soon as possible. Please immediately contact us if you become aware that a child under 16 has provided us with personal information.

Revisions of this Privacy Policy

This Privacy Policy is valid from 20.10.2022 and replaces any other previous notifications that we had issued in the past regarding our personal data management practices. We reserve the right to revise this Policy at any time. The current version will always be uploaded to our website indicating the date of entry into force, so you know when the most recent revision took place. If there are critical changes in this Policy or our personal data practices change significantly in the future, we will notify you by posting the changes on our website.

Annex C2. Information Sheet

The Information Sheet provides information on the project, the duration, contact details and information on the rights of individuals providing data. It can be personalized to specific project activity where personal data is to be collected.

We would like to invite you to take part in an activity being carried out by the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project, a 3-year project funded by the European Union within the framework of the Horizon Europe program. Take some time to read this information sheet and if you have questions feel free to reach us.

What is the SUSTCERTBIOBASED project about?

Biobased products play a prominent role in the transition from a fossil-based economy to a circular economy at an EU and global level. According to an assessment done by the European Commission, biobased products can contribute to a more sustainable economy and could represent approximately €57 billion in annual income and involve 300.000 jobs.¹

But what exactly are biobased products? Biobased products are wholly or partially made from materials of biological origin. Even though they could help reduce greenhouse gas emissions and offer other advantages such as lower levels of toxicity or novel product characteristics (e.g. biodegradability), it is still very important to ensure their sustainability on environmental, social and economic dimensions.

There are plenty of sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels that have been developed to track the sustainability impacts of biobased products. However, given the fact that there is no harmonization of these certification schemes yet, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project will contribute to defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainable certification schemes and business-to-business labels. The project will lay the foundation to support a faster and smoother transition to a circular, sustainable bioeconomy!

It will do so by developing a monitoring system to evaluate the effectiveness and robustness of existing certification schemes and labels and assessing the feasibility of adoption of certification schemes and labels by taking into consideration costs and benefits (including internalized environmental and social ones). The results of the project as well as the insights gained along the way will be used to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policymakers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. Within the next years the multidisciplinary consortium of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project will

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/biotechnology/bio-based-products_en

organise several events and workshops to inform the audience about important findings and updates on the progress of the project. Additionally, a Network of Interest consisting of at least 50 members will be developed to facilitate the international networking, dialogue and knowledge exchange across industrial biobased value chain actors and the sustainability system community.

Useful Information

Is my participation voluntary and what will it involve?

Your participation in the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project is entirely voluntary. If you decide to participate in a SUSTCERT4BIOBASED activity, you will be asked to sign an **Informed Consent Form** to collect and process your data. The project will last for 36 months but your involvement will last as long as you wish.

Purpose of personal data collection

[To be adjusted based on the purpose of data collection, example is provided below for the purpose of Network of Interest]

The role of the Network of Interest (NoI) is to provide a platform where members can interact, receive project updates, and share their knowledge and views on bioeconomy and sustainability certification related aspects. To effectively conduct this, we would need to process some of your personal data:

- Your contact details;
- Demographics (age, gender, country of origin)
- Professional information (where you are working, what is your job position, which is the area of your expertise)
- Personal opinions on the topic

What we will do with your data

The information you provide is **confidential**. Your consent form will be kept separate from the observations collected during the course of the project activity. We will share your data with other SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project partners that are involved in the data analysis and reporting process. Once the data is analysed, a report of the findings may be submitted for publication. The project's deliverables that will be derived by this activity will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. The results of this project activity might be also shared with European Union representatives (e.g., the Project Officer evaluating the project's progress, auditing EU agencies). Only broad trends will be reported, and **it will not be possible to identify any individuals**.

Are there any risks involved?

No, there are no risks involved.

Access, deletion of information, or consent withdrawal

According to the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), you have the right to request:

- I. a copy of your data;

- II. correction of your data, if you think they are not accurate;
- III. to delete your data;
- IV. to limit or stop processing your personal data;
- V. to give you your data in an appropriate format and transfer them to another organisation.

You can also withdraw your consent and, therefore, your participation at any time without consequences. In case of anonymous data already collected, keep in mind that will be used since we cannot trace the information back to you. Further data would not be collected, or any other procedure would not be carried out in relation to your information.

In case you wish to verify the personal data we store, to modify, correct, delete or request a consent withdrawal you may communicate with the responsible partner listed below.

Contact Information

Partner name: [partner collecting data]

e-mail: info@sustcert4biobased.eu, [email from partner collecting data]

Website: sustcert4biobased.eu

Annex C3. Informed Consent Form

The Informed Consent Form is used for participation in activities of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project to agree on collecting and processing of the participant's data. It can be personalized to specific project activity where personal data is to be collected.

I confirm that I understand that by ticking each box below I am consenting to this element of the study. I understand that it will be assumed that unticked boxes mean that I DO NOT consent to that part of the study. I also understand that by not giving consent for any of the elements, I may be deemed ineligible for participating in this project's activity.

I confirm that I have been given an explanation of the purpose of the project's activities. I have read and understood the Information Sheet which I was provided with or listened to an explanation about the project by a project partner.

I have had an opportunity to consider what kind of information will be expected of me. I have also had the opportunity to ask questions and clarifications about the requested information which have been answered to my satisfaction.

I agree to appear in pictures/videos that might be taken during project activities as evidence of any activity itself and as promotional material for the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project. I understand that these pictures will not be provided to any organisation for commercial purposes. However, they may be processed by third parties as a consequence of their dissemination at international level through the project's social media and website.

I understand that the consortium has no control on the images after dissemination.

I agree that my anonymised research data may be used by others for future research (I will not be identifiable when this data is shared).

I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason, and that any data after the time of which it is withdrawn will be no longer included as part of any future reports, unless I agree.

I understand that my personal data will be held and processed in confidence and in accordance with the principles laid out by GDPR.

I am aware of whom I should contact if I wish to lodge a complaint.

I confirm that I have read and understood the above information and freely consent to participate in activities of the project. I have been given adequate time to consider my participation.

About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry.

PARTNERS

Stichting Wageningen Research (WR)
www.wur.nl

Fundacion Circe Centro de Investigacion de Recursos y Consumos Energeticos (CIRCE)
www.fcirce.es

White Research SRL (WHITE)
white-research.eu

Environmental Coalition on Standards (ECOS)
www.ecostandard.org

Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH (CU)
www.controlunion-germany.com

CONTACT US

info@sustcert4biobased.eu

- Sustcert4biobased
- @SUSTCERT4BIO
- SUSTCERT4BIOBASED
- SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

VISIT

www.sustcert4biobased.eu